

ReCreate
Reusing precast concrete for a circular economy

Paul Jonker-Hoffrén

**Educational Needs in
Deconstruction and Reuse of
Precast Concrete Elements**

Publisher / project	Reusing precast concrete for a circular economy
Project acronym	ReCreate
Deliverable	D8.5 Roadmap for Educational Needs
Lead beneficiary	TAU
Author(s)	Paul Jonker-Hoffrén
Dissemination level	Public
Cite this document	Jonker-Hoffrén, P. (2025). <i>Educational Needs in Deconstruction and Reuse of Precast Concrete Elements</i> . The ReCreate project.
Disclaimer	The content presented herein reflect the authors' views. The European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information this publication contains.

Abstract

The ReCreate project researches reusing precast concrete elements, not originally designed for disassembly, through real-life deconstruction and reuse pilots in four European countries. The current report sheds light on the main learning issues that emerged from the project's deconstruction pilots.

The transition to the circular economy will need new skills: either reconfiguration of existing skills, or fully new skills (and jobs). The European Union has emphasised the importance of the construction sector in the Green Transition. The current report is based on empirical material from ReCreate's deconstruction pilots. It takes a look at the skills needs in the circular construction sector for the most relevant actors. In ReCreate, very few completely new skills have been identified. Most skills needed in the pilots have been reconfigured skills. These are skills that can be found in the linear economy but can be reconfigured for circular work processes. This is good news from the viewpoint of the Green Transition because it enables existing and future construction sector employees to work in the circular construction economy with their current skills. This may also bring new kind of people into the sector, including women, as the *goal* of the work has changed; the creation of new *meaningful* work is important for e.g. Millennials. However, there are certain skills that must be developed further, which may also bring new people in the sector and create new jobs. Prime among these are data management, environmental impact assessment and Building Information Modelling based skills in relation to material passports/digitalisation for deconstruction planners, authorities, structural engineers, and architects.

One overarching (transversal, i.e. generally applicable) skill need relates to *communication and knowledge*. The success of circular processes lies in knowledge and information sharing. ReCreate's pilots have shown that information (about materials, processes, etc.) may have to be shared between actors at a very early stage because acts at one stage may affect later stages. This kind of 'path dependency' of materials and information requires a kind of 'forward and backward thinking' that may be new to project management, as actors may have to consider what information may be needed at a certain stage. It can be aided by knowledge of the requirements of public authorities, too. Assessment criteria and permit processes change and may require new information about materials and processes. As these criteria are to some extent in flux and certainly not settled, it is useful if the project manager has access to experts in public policy. A previous ReCreate report (Halonen et al., 2024) provides a broad overview for ReCreate pilot countries to aid this part of project management.

The current report concludes with recommendations for educational institutions. Most of them should be valid for circular work in any complicated value chain. The main recommendations are to increase collaboration projects between universities, universities of applied sciences, and vocational education institutions (aimed at transversal skills), and to integrate engineering and architecture studies to a greater extent with public administration courses and vice versa (aimed at technical skills).

Contents

1.	Introduction.....	1
2.	Materials knowledge and digitalisation.....	6
2.1.	Materials knowledge.....	6
2.1.1.	Materials knowledge matters in circular economy.....	7
2.1.2.	Materials knowledge is connected to expertise.....	8
2.2.	Digitalisation.....	10
2.2.1.	Building Information Modelling.....	10
2.2.2.	Digital material passports.....	11
3.	Skill needs of professions.....	14
3.1.	Deconstruction.....	14
3.1.1.	The use of tools as an educational need.....	17
3.2.	Precast concrete factories.....	19
3.3.	Logistics.....	22
3.4.	Quality control.....	23
3.5.	Structural engineers.....	25
3.5.1.	Tools for structural engineering.....	26
3.6.	Architects.....	28
3.7.	Multi-actor processes.....	30
4.	Discussion and conclusions.....	31
4.1.	Limitations.....	33
5.	Recommendations.....	34
6.	References.....	36

List of abbreviations

BIM	Building information modelling
CEDEFOP	European Centre for the Development of Vocational Training
CPR	Construction Products Regulation
CSR	Corporate social responsibility
CSRD	Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive
DPP	Digital Product Passport
ESCO	Classification of European Skills, Competences, and Occupations
ESG	Environmental, social and governance
ICT	Information and communication technology
LCA	Life cycle assessment
STEM	Science, technology, engineering, and mathematics
VET	Vocational education and training

Acknowledgements

Erik Stenberg (KTH), Jukka Lahdensivu, Satu Huuhka, Aapo Räsänen and Emmi Salmio (TAU), and Eric Rawlins (Like Architects) provided content and feedback to this report.

1. Introduction

The transition to a circular construction economy demands new skills. This skill transition is different for different professions. The main idea is that in the circular economy, work processes are aimed at circularity rather than virgin materials. Therefore, behind the skills transition there is a form of rethinking materials. This introduction sketches the logic of skill transition for the use of prefabricated concrete elements.

According to a recent report from the European Training Foundation, the 'greening' of traditional jobs, like those in the construction sector, is key to the Green Transition.¹ ReCreate Work Package 8 is concerned with policy support and social acceptability. In practice, social acceptability relates to the study of work processes and employment. This includes assessing which skills are needed in the circular construction economy. During the pilot projects in Finland, Germany and the Netherlands observational research and interviews have been performed to study work processes. In this ReCreate field work, underlying the current report, one respondent pondered the following about skills in the circular economy:

'Skill development is essential for the successful transition to circular development, design and construction. In essence reuse, whether concerning buildings or materials, represents a significantly different approach to the physical world we live in. Recognising that construction is never an end unto itself emphasises this significance.'

In the context of the ReCreate project, this appears to be apt, as the empirical research on skills and work processes shows that it is mostly the *approach* to construction that is starkly different from construction in the linear economy. Work in the ReCreate pilots has shown that there is skill *updating*, and the expectation is that circular construction will require an increase in the labour force, as parts of the processes are labour intensive.

As further explained in Chapter 3, this approach is a fundamental change. It does not only affect firms in the construction sector through policy, but through a fundamental rethinking of what construction is. If the message of the policy environment is taken seriously, the future of construction will be about management of resources, rather than endlessly erecting new buildings with resources extracted locally or elsewhere. This change in approach may not so much influence the skill demands of blue-collar workers in the sector. However, for white-collar professions, such as architects and structural engineers, it is a new way of thinking. As soon discussed in Section 3.4, structural engineers may have to start seeing their profession more as an art or craft because are more 'unknowns' in the reuse of materials. Some of these can be eliminated but others will persist. Still, if materials performed their function in a donor building, why would those good characteristics suddenly be lost? Rethinking material use does to some extent represent a 'leap of faith',

¹ <https://www.etf.europa.eu/en/green2024>

which may be challenging to the mostly conservative construction sector. Also, for architects, the new approach makes a fundamental difference because they need to start their design with existing materials and parts that come with limitations, e.g. dimensions. Rather than starting from an empty paper, many aspects are already given. Therefore, the new approach to construction, which ReCreate is testing through its pilots, does not only need some new skills, but first and foremost needs, in teaching at the universities, the education of young professionals who *think* differently. In addition, as explained in Chapter 3, professionals of all kinds need knowledge of policy *and* technology.

The policy environment is quickly moving towards the mainstreaming of circular economy principles. This can be seen equally in the updated European Union (EU) Construction Product Regulation (CPR)², the Waste Directive³, the European Green Deal⁴ and the incentives in the EU Taxonomy.⁵ These have in common that they are all intended to reshape the European economy in a fundamental way. The EU must work according to the provision of the Treaty on European Union⁶ which means that its instruments are largely aimed at how the European Single Market works and how interventions relate to the freedom of movement of people, services, goods and capital. Although the European Council has published many important labour market Directives (e.g. the Parental Leave Directive⁷ and the Minimum Wage Directive⁸), these are intrinsically connected to the principles of the EU: free markets and free movement of people and goods. All other labour market issues remain the exclusive domain of the Member States. On the topic of skills and education, the EU has been dealing with education, training and skills for specific actions dedicated to the (twin) green and digital transitions. These include a Communication from the Commission on achieving the European Education Area by 2025⁹ and a Council Recommendation on vocational education and training (VET) for sustainable competitiveness, social fairness and resilience.¹⁰ These are non-binding instruments, but they may be used for guidance on the interpretation of EU law.

Nonetheless, the EU has not been inactive regarding labour market issues that are connected to the circular economy or the Green Transition. The most relevant EU actor in this field is the European Centre for the Development of Vocational Training (CEDEFOP), which was (re)founded by Regulation (EU) 2019/128 of the European Parliament and of the Council.¹¹ It was originally founded in 1975, but the 2019 Regulation explicitly included the issue of skills and qualifications policies in its mandate. The agency explicitly has an aim for knowledge production for policymaking at the EU and national levels. Here, it is important

² <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2024/3110/oj>

³ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dir/2008/98/oj/eng>

⁴ https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/priorities-2019-2024/european-green-deal_en

⁵ https://finance.ec.europa.eu/regulation-and-supervision/financial-services-legislation/implementing-and-delegated-acts/taxonomy-regulation_en

⁶ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX:12016ME/TXT&from=EN#d1e32-13-1>

⁷ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dir/2010/18/oj/eng>

⁸ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dir/2022/2041/oj/eng>

⁹ COM/2020/625 final, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex:52020DC0625>

¹⁰ [https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX:32020H1202\(01\)&from=EN](https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX:32020H1202(01)&from=EN)

¹¹ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2019/128/oj/eng>

to emphasise the agency is tri-partite, meaning that it works together with the social partners (labour unions and employers' associations) towards its goal. The input from these actors in the knowledge production provide an essential link with developments 'on the ground'.

Another important actor is the European Training Foundation (ETF), with whom CEDEFOP works closely together. The Foundation was established in 2008, and its work is geared towards the human capital development in countries neighbouring the EU. Although its aim is therefore outside the EU, the Foundation works to transfer best practices and knowledge from the current Member states to countries in various stages of accession. In this context, the Foundation has also produced valuable knowledge on skills and the Green Transition.¹²

While more a tool than an agency, the European Skills, Competences, Qualifications and Occupations (ESCO) jobs and skills classification has been recently updated with a new taxonomy of green skills.¹³ This database is useful to ascertain the skills needed for e.g. a solar panel installation professional. In the technical report for the database, various forms of skills are based on a skills hierarchy, a knowledge concepts hierarchy and a transversal skills hierarchy. These are connected to 'green concepts', which are defined by the essential and optional relationship with occupations, skill reusability types, and the allocation in the respective hierarchies. For example, the occupation 'building construction worker' has many essential skills, like mixing concrete, using safety equipment and working in a team¹⁴. Optional skills related to this occupation can include windows-setting and tile laying (among many other things.) Also various types of knowledge may be optional, such as knowledge building construction principles or knowing types of concrete pumps. Mixing concrete for instance, according to the database, is a skill that is reusable as it is defined as cross-sector applicable. In the skills hierarchy, mixing concrete is a subcategory of the skill 'preparing mixtures or solutions' and below it is the skill 'feed concrete mixer'. The ESCO database therefore, at an abstract level, shows what people in specific occupations need in terms of skill and knowledge development. These aspects of occupations and tasks can be used to identify educational needs in the circular construction sector – in particular because the ESCO skill descriptions are quite general.

The current report – Roadmap for Educational Needs – is informed by the publications and research produced by the ETF and CEDEFOP, but it focuses on the practices observed in the real-life deconstruction and reuse pilots of ReCreate. Findings regarding educational needs are essential to the social acceptability of the Green Transition because most of people's time awake is spent working, and the education needed for the work carries the ideas and values of the Green Transition. Education is a way to make the Green Transition inclusive. This is emphasised in the construction sector, which is currently mostly linear, but potentially can be circular. There is great potential in employment with a transition to a

¹² <https://www.etf.europa.eu/en/what-we-do/skills-demands-analysis>

¹³ <https://esco.ec.europa.eu/en/about-esco/publications/publication/green-skills-and-knowledge-concepts-labelling-esco>

¹⁴ <https://esco.ec.europa.eu/en/classification/occupation?uri=http://data.europa.eu/esco/occupation/fb7e2f4f-1545-42f1-972e-94082e49c6dc>

circular construction sector. As Fielden et al. (2000) already stated, the construction sector has a problem of labour supply, which is partly of its own making due to cultural and recruitment traits. The construction sector is not often seen as an attractive career choice because of its reputation as heavy, dirty work (Ayodele et al., 2020; ELA, 2021). Supanti and Butcher (2019) show that meaningful work is an important value for Millennials (Generation Y). As circularity is a tool and a value for Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) at the same time, this may make the construction sector more attractive. In short, the *values* inherent in circular construction work reconfigure skills at an *ideational* level, even though they are nominally the same skills as in a linear setting.

The remainder of this introduction discusses a recent report by CEDEFOP and looks at its conclusions regarding the construction sector. After this introduction, the educational needs of core actors in the construction sector production chain will be discussed, followed by discussion and conclusions, as well as recommendations to educational institutions.

The CEDEFOP 2023 report 'Skills in transition – the way to 2035' details the trends and challenges in European working life.¹⁵ Although CEDEFOP is nominally concerned with Vocational Education and Training (VET), the report discusses labour markets and skill needs more broadly. It starts from the observation that in many sectors, there is a labour shortage, which in some cases is also a skills shortage, but it can also be an indicator of a lack of *decent* work. The report aims to discuss both supply- and demand-side issues. For example, sectors like STEM and ICT face labour shortages because people do not have the right skills. Ageing of the European population is also a significant cause for labour shortages. The report identifies two drivers to labour market developments: the digital transition and the green transition. CEDEFOP also sees that job growth in the near future will be dominated by skills-dominated work in services and manufacturing. Specifically, the report emphasises the role of job upgrading: the importance of medium or high skilling for jobs in many sectors. In relation to the twin drivers of labour market developments, the green transition is identified as a skills transition, requiring an inclusive skilling revolution involving workers across qualification and seniority levels, sectors and occupations. This observation in the report means a watershed change from the current situation, especially considering the labour market participation of women. It essentially requires not only an upgrading of skills but, as per Fielden et al. (2000), the company and sectoral culture also must change. The report discusses the skills needed for the green transition, ranging from technical to transversal and the importance of embedding them across education and training programmes.

The report acknowledges that especially the construction sector is a prime candidate for 'greening job development' and it expects job growth because of the importance of the construction sector for the Green Transition, primarily because of the need for renovations and the construction of circular economy-related facilities (recycling plants etc.). However, an earlier CEDEFOP report sketches a scenario in which the sector will see a decline in

¹⁵ https://www.cedefop.europa.eu/files/4213_en.pdf

employment growth from 2021-2035.¹⁶ This scenario is based on the end of the so-called 'Renovation Wave' and trends like retirement and job changes between sectors, which do leave a significant number of job openings in the construction sector (see footnote 15, p. 44). This prediction does not quite match with the drift of the report in general, which sees job upgrading in nearly all sectors as a prerequisite for the Green Transition and argues for an increased attractiveness of jobs of all levels in the sector. The CEDEFOP report anticipates employment growth primarily from twin digital and green transitions, e.g. regarding architects (BIM) and engineering services, because these are seen as core occupations for European Green Deal sectors, such as construction. The report argues that these transitions require more highly qualified employees in the construction sector, because it makes a transition from crafts-based professions to more knowledge-based professions. The CEDEFOP report thus gives a clear approach to skills needs in the circular economy. One must look at transversal (general) skills and technical skills. These aspects will be discussed next in more detail.

¹⁶ <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/937a7230-7a6a-11ec-9136-01aa75ed71a1/language-en>

2. Materials knowledge and digitalisation

In a circular construction sector, professionals need both technical knowledge and transversal skills. This is similar to the linear construction sector, but there are differences. The key new skills relate to communication and knowledge transfer between actors in the value chain¹⁷. Understanding the knowledge needs of actors in the value chain will be a critical determining factor for the success of a circular project, and in the future after its completion. Skills and knowledge are intimately connected (Collins & Evans, 2007), and in all professions of the circular value chain, both skills and knowledge of materials and digitalisation are essential. Section 2.2 discusses the relevance of materials knowledge, while Section 2.3 explores digitalisation. Here, 'materials knowledge' refers not only to the material characteristics but also to the product characteristics, as for professionals engaged with concrete elements, both kinds of characteristics are relevant. While the analysis of these topics is based on ReCreate's experience on deconstructing precast concrete elements, it is likely that many aspects will be applicable to the circular use of products made of other materials as well. Sector and profession-specific skills needs are discussed in Section 2.4.

2.1. Materials knowledge

The knowledge of materials is essential for all construction. However, for the circular construction sector, the relevance may be much higher, as there are many regulatory demands reclaimed materials and products should adhere to if they are to be reused as construction products¹⁸. There are many reasons why knowledge of reclaimed materials and products is essential to the circular construction sector, but the most important one is to ensure the product is indeed still suitable for continued use. In addition, materials knowledge is important to ensure the products are still suitable for use from a health point of view – this is one reason why also in traditional demolition, there is an analysis of potential hazardous substances. Furthermore, these analyses are important to improve the social acceptability of reuse of materials and products because if they are deemed safe, then it is easier for consumers (e.g. homebuyers) and other end-users (office workers, teachers, persons in hospital care etc.) to trust the quality of the building. This is especially important given the prevalence of indoor air quality issues (see Kumar et al., 2023).

The ReCreate contribution to the Tallinn Architecture Biennale in 2024 shows this in stark contrast¹⁹. There are two videos, involving the same company. One shows the

¹⁷ See Jonker-Hoffrén (2023).

¹⁸ See Halonen et al. (2024), Halonen et al. (2025), Räsänen et al. (2024a) and Räsänen et al. (2024b).

¹⁹ <https://recreate-project.eu/tallinn-architecture-biennale-2024/>

deconstruction of the Finnish ReCreate donor building, and the other shows a traditional demolition. In the latter one, it seems material knowledge is less relevant because everything is demolished, though in a planned manner, using the same tools (a demolition crane), and the process is far removed from craft work because of the tool and the manner of working. Besides the implied driver of the crane (and the smaller excavator), the only human visible in this video is an employee in a yellow safety vest who enters a storage container. By contrast, the deconstruction video shows a lot of human activity – more specifically, activity in an engagement between human, tools, and material. For example, a hole is drilled, after which a worker uses a hook to raise the hoisting sling handed over by another worker below. There is a lot of manoeuvring, controlling of machines, feeling, and interaction with the materials. This looks like craft work. The comparison between two ways of ‘removing a building’ shows that for deconstruction, skilled workers are needed with knowledge of the materials and products they work with. Workers also need to be more sensitive in the use of tools for disconnecting for reuse.

The future educational needs for the circular construction economy must focus on materials knowledge. This is a demand at the individual level, but it extends also to the organisational level and between actors in a project. The next section will discuss the nature of expertise in this context, after which it is expanded on *why* knowledge of materials is such an essential aspect of information transfer in the circular economy.

2.1.1. Materials knowledge matters in circular economy

The construction sector produces, consumes and discards enormous amounts of materials. Innovations in material production can help reach the EU’s goal of a zero-carbon economy, but compared to the masses of materials that exist, these innovations are but a drop in the sea. Materials knowledge matters in this situation, whether for renovation or reuse. Compared to virgin building, the need for materials knowledge is most simply expressed by the term ‘non-standard.’ Existing products have a history – a pattern of use along with time-induced changes in material characteristics. These may not always matter for reuse, but the fact that buildings are changing entities at various time scales is something to take into consideration with reuse. Although ‘standardised’ in a construction drawing and in the construction product factories, by the time it is physically constructed, the building is already unique (see Brand, 1995). In practice, there are always deviations from the construction drawings. The deviations are accounted for through the calculation of tolerances, but deviations may also occur through a different choice of materials at the construction company (because of price, availability, etc.). Furthermore, there may be deviations in construction methods to more conservative methods or to methods the builder is accustomed to, or to reach a preferred level of certainty. All these deviations are (supposedly) discussed or negotiated with the client, but the important issue is whether changes are properly documented. For example, in the Finnish deconstruction pilot, there was initially a delay in detaching façade panels because they were connected differently than described in the construction plans. This meant the deconstruction workers had to recognise the material and connection that was used and change the process, after consulting with the structural engineer, for detaching the panels. Once this was achieved, the panels did not pose a challenge anymore.

By the time a building is selected for deconstruction, a large amount of information is needed to assess whether its constitutive parts can be reused. Furthermore, a substantial amount of knowledge about connections and how they behave is needed –including knowledge about the materials that need to be cut or removed to get to the connections in the first place. This and other information exists in many forms, and a challenge for reuse can be the need for the role of ‘data archaeologists’, since it is not clear which actor in the value chain should take the lead. As discussed in a previous ReCreate report (Jonker-Hoffrén, 2023), information needed and produced in the circular value chain does not necessarily match timewise. In the circular construction value chain, pieces of information about the products are produced at different stages. This happens not only through (formal) testing of the materials, but also because in work processes, the products are changed (e.g. in terms of dimensions, connections, spalling or cracking on the surface) and the information on the original construction should be taken into account as well. Materials knowledge thus also changes during the journey of the product in the value chain. This is one of the reasons why the idea of a ‘material passport’ is so important, in that it systematically documents changes. Material passports are a necessary requirement for the transition to the circular construction economy, because for reuse it is adamant to know what the building blocks of the future are.

2.1.2. Materials knowledge is connected to expertise

As Collins (2007; 2004) has shown, there are significant parts of knowledge that cannot be codified. This can be called ‘embodied’ knowledge, or with a more general term, tacit knowledge. These forms of knowledge are transversal and technical at the same time. They are generally applicable because they exist in the brain and body of an employee. These skills can be applied to different situations, depending on what the task requires. The tacit knowledge skills depend very much on experience and muscle memory. However, the discussion of tacit knowledge is not limited to social sciences. Also Pallasmaa (2009) discusses the links between mental and muscle knowledge, particular the use of hands in crafts from shoemaking to dentistry and architecture.

Materials knowledge is partly tacit knowledge. Deconstruction employees know from experience how materials react when handling them, in ways that words cannot always easily capture. It is the bodily feeling which connects the material through the tool with the brain and body. For example, when cutting a concrete seam, the employee notices when the saw has gone through. This is a feeling that is experienced; a foreman cannot give exact instruction as to what the process is like – it is gained through experience and learning. In this case using the saw, there is a resistance with disappears when the blade goes through. This description is sufficient, but experiencing this phenomenon is necessary to understand the meaning. Furthermore, the deconstruction employee has to learn to anticipate *when* this phenomenon happens, as to potentially be able to exercise the necessary caution and precision. This is true for both routine operations and situations where some kind of improvisation is needed to execute the tasks assigned.

Without going too deep in the sociology/philosophy of work, in the context of circular work it is important to note that in sociology, 'work' can be defined as the activities that people undertake to achieve a goal; they follow instructions but also use their judgement and skills to make decisions to take independent action (e.g. Jakonen et al., 2025; Wisner, 1995; Deranty, 2009). Thus, for example the deconstruction plan forms the context for a myriad of tasks to be accomplished, but it is the people who perform actions and make judgements with knowledge and experience to do this. This view of work is not limited to manual work but applies equally to knowledge work and service work. In architecture (and perhaps engineering) knowledge of the composition of materials is important, although people in these functions are relatively far away from the actual tactile construction. In these different forms of work, technical skills, experience, and tools are important. In architecture, the term tectonics is used for describing the processes above: 'the science or art of construction, both in relation to use and artistic design.' (Maulden, 1986; Frampton, 2001). The advantage of studying work as a process that connects embodied knowledge to the skilled use of tools is also that difficulties in the process can be understood better. A problem in a work process can be broken down and assessed for the employee's skills, the tools used to solve to problem and the material/product characteristics. Such a holistic approach can lead to more efficient learning and better process management. This approach also implies that the activity called 'work' cannot be fully taught in educational facilities because it is dependent on experience as well as materials.

The point of the pilots in ReCreate is to learn about reuse, and also about the work processes necessary for reuse. But reuse is not a simple recipe - it can be nearly seen as the tip of an iceberg, where skills, experience and tacit knowledge are somewhat hidden from view below the readily visible aspects of work. A large part of the skill needs that emerged in the deconstruction pilots have been learnt while in working life. For example, using drills, demolition robots or diamond saws are typically the kind of tasks where an elder teaches how the tool works, and the rest is trial and error. Also issues like work safety may need *ad hoc* learning or innovations: in ReCreate's Dutch pilot, the way the deconstruction was planned required a different solution for the safety fences. The normal practice of placing safety fencing would hinder deconstruction, therefore a new type of safety fencing was devised, which was attached with special clamps through window openings²⁰. The use of general tools can be taught in educational institutions, but in practice businesses may use new, unique or specialised equipment that may not be useful for e.g. vocational schools to acquire. On the other hand, engineers and architects use specialised but widely used computer programs, which should therefore be part of the curriculum.

Material and product knowledge is the basis for circular expertise. However, it is not only the products but also their connection with 'deposited knowledge', such as construction drawings and calculations, processes of architectural design, and quality tests. This 'deposited knowledge' is necessary for the 'translation' of materials and products of one donor building to the new context of a circular construction. The role of architects is emphasised in these processes, in that they can be the linchpins in these 'translation'

²⁰ See Halonen et al. (2025), Section 4.4.

processes; innovative design using reusable materials needs both imagination and understanding of the technical issues involved. The ReCreate project shows the importance of knowledge sharing and communication at the crossroads between architecture and structural engineering, with necessary feedback between these professionals.

2.2. Digitalisation

2.2.1. Building Information Modelling

The use of BIM for deconstruction is central in the ReCreate project and is discussed extensively in another report (Vullings et al., 2022). However, in this section, BIM is looked at as a skill to master in parallel to policy developments. As this report notes, the uptake of BIM in the EU area is rather uneven. Miltera-Kielbasa and Zima (2024), in a rare policy overview of BIM requirements, show that the adoption of BIM has taken place mostly in the West and North of the EU, although many countries have plans for BIM implementation. In ReCreate this could also be seen, as BIM was fairly unknown to the German partners, who are arguably the most experienced in construction with reused precast concrete (starting from the 1990s). Although reuse is certainly possible without BIM, BIM is nevertheless *critical* to scaling up reuse because it simplifies information flows. The EU's BIM Taskgroup in 2020 recommends that public procurement is to be used to progressively introduce BIM to public project tenders and contracts²¹. In this sense, the uptake of BIM is dependent on the extent it is required in public procurement. This means that the need to learn BIM skills is rather dependent on the national policy environment. According to the EU BIM Taskforce's Handbook, it is not only about skills in operating computer programs, but it also creates a new need for data managements skills. These skills have implications for employees at different levels in firms and across the value chain – there are general issues of responsibility and control, but also practical matters relating to the worksite. In Finland, the non-ReCreate 'Mobiilipomo' ('Mobile Boss') project at the Turku School of Economics studied the implications for management of introducing new digital technologies at the workplace.²² At the same institution, an EU-funded project on digital skills in the construction sector produced a guide that focused on basic skills and critical reading skills in the internet context. This study shows that there may be a large gap between what is possible with mobile BIM applications, and the knowledge base of construction workers. The project's report is available only in Finnish, but it includes an assessment tool to gauge digital preparedness of workers.

The Finnish project 'DigiPurku' ('Digital demolition') aims to simplify demolition, deconstruction and (potentially reuse) through digitalisation²³. The project employs BIM models to plan and execute demolition. ReCreate's Jonker-Hoffrén, the author of the current report, has been in the so-called 'reference group' of the project to comment and discuss

²¹ https://www.eubim.eu/wp-content/uploads/2017/07/EUBIM_Handbook_Web_Optimized-1.pdf, p. 54.

²² <https://sites.utu.fi/digiraksa/mopo/>

²³ <https://gnf.fi/en/digipurku/>

their progress. In many ways, it has been similar to the first stages of the ReCreate deconstruction planning and execution, but the project stops at that phase. Like in ReCreate, data is collected for the deconstruction, but currently there is no planning for reuse. The clear difference with ReCreate is therefore that ReCreate connects all parts of the chain, from historical surveys, pre-deconstruction audit to quality assurance and redesign, all with the use of digital models. Compared to the aforementioned projects, the information handles digitally in the ReCreate project, although it may not be contained in a single model.

BIM modelling also has a blind spot: although very useful, it ignores the materiality of construction products, especially changes that happen during the deconstruction process. In a sense, BIM modelling is 'platonic' in that (for deconstruction) building products are measured and in the modelling, only these measurements are taken into account. The deconstruction process, however, may have significant effects on the dimensions of building products. For the reuse phase, the refurbished products will nonetheless be remodelled according to their current state, at least in ReCreate's Finnish cluster. Indeed, it would be useful to distinguish between different phases of the model that is made of the elements. The inventory model for deconstruction is based on historical drawings, laser scanning, etc. This is sufficient for the deconstruction phase. For reuse, on the other hand, new information must be added, which comes from testing, refurbishment, and the intended reuse. Reclaimed concrete elements are not, as a rule, immediately ready for reuse but require refurbishment. In it, dimensions of some products (e.g. hollow-core slabs) were changed. This information is added to the BIM model in the reuse phase. There is thus a need for different models, and acknowledging/documenting the processes of refurbishing the reclaimed elements in the BIM model may be of importance in reuse (e.g. regarding permitting processes).

A BIM model of a building can be highly useful for deconstruction but since the donor building does not exist after the deconstruction takes place, the model should be updated regarding the products: a discrepancy would otherwise exist between the 'original' pre-deconstruction products in the BIM model, and the 'real' post-deconstruction products. There may be many implementation difficulties, but the goal is to implement knowledge from about construction systems (element types) and quality assurance in the BIM model or in several models/data repositories using (preferably) standardised data management methodologies. Also here, communication between actors in the supply chain is vital.

2.2.2. Digital material passports

From 2027, the EU's new Construction Product Regulation (CPR, Article 75 onwards) requires construction products to have a Digital Product Passport (DPP), which would also integrate with BIM modelling and enable transparency regarding environmental impact of products.²⁴ The description of the technical and regulatory contents regarding DPPs is outside the scope of this report. Nonetheless, its relevance here is the impact it may have

²⁴ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2024/3110/oj> and <https://data.europa.eu/en/news-events/news/eus-digital-product-passport-advancing-transparency-and-sustainability>

on skill needs. For the moment, pending so-called delegated acts, the requirement of a DPP seems to apply to only *new* construction products with a strong focus on future reuse (in line with the Ecodesign Directive)²⁵. However, material passports are considered to be a significant source of value for reused construction products because of the data they contain on *existing* construction products (Debacker et al., 2016).

Literature on material passports and digital product passports is vast and constantly renewing because regulations change. In this sense, the DPP is a welcome change because it anchors, for the foreseeable future, what a material passport means in the European context. Two recent research articles summarise the state of affairs regarding digital product passports, including conceptual clarification about the difference between a material passport and a DPP. The former is specific to the built environment and (currently) not part of any regulation. It focuses on materials/products, i.e. is specific to raw materials, element products (e.g. hollow-core slabs) and geographical areas. The DPP, on the other hand, is concerned with products (rather than materials), has a cross-industry focus, and is enshrined in the CPR and the Ecodesign Directive (Markou et al., 2025). In their literature review of recent research on material passports, Markou et al. (2025) find several distinct thematic categories, of which the BIM-based material passport is the most significant. Research on practical dimensions of material passport come to the fore through organisational aspects such as platform-based, blockchain-based and GIS/RFID/QR-code based passports. GIS-based material passports are an attempt to collect data about building materials at various locations. The final thematic category concerns data requirements (Markou et al., 2025: 14). It is safe to say that depending on regulatory or project requirements, the material passport can include nearly an infinity of different data aspects. Dervishaj and Gudmundsson (2024) show, in a comprehensive review, what digital tools are available and how a digital workflow can be improved to achieve circular economy goals.

Van Capelleveen et al. (2023) also perform a literature study of material passes but use a much broader dataset that stretches back to the earliest incidence of the idea. The value of this article is that they focus on the many forms of a material passport that have existed – albeit with different names, like recycling passports or resource passports. They distinguish between whether the material passports documented are mandated by regulation or so-called ‘personally designed indicators’ (Van Capelleveen et al., 2023: 8). The latter means the concepts, data formats or units of analysis are other than what is mandated by law, such as energy use scores or researcher-designed deconstructability scores. For the current report, it is relevant that the authors differentiate between the roles of different stakeholders and the risks and uncertainties during the product life cycle, as e.g. ownership has an impact on this issue (see also Debacker et al., 2016). Related to this is their review of issues of data governance, which they discuss in five categories: generation and maintenance, standardised exchange, ownership, confidentiality, and integrity and accuracy. The first category includes BIM modelling but also the use of sensors, IoT and

²⁵<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32024R1781&qid=1719580391746>

manual data entry. The core challenge here, regardless of technology, is the quality of the data and the incentives of stakeholders to provide/produce data. The second category is focused on the longevity of data and how it is ensured that data will be understandable (or even readable) in the future, especially since there is not yet a single standard for data collection and maintenance. The third category, ownership, focuses on the ownership of data (as part of intellectual property rights) and how the ownership is transferred to new owners of the material/product. Confidentiality, the fourth category, is related to the incentives of owners/producers to disclose information that can be considered a business secret. Finally, integrity and accuracy relate to the ability of materials passports to aid with sustainability auditing and are therefore also related to data quality.

The details of these categories are highly interesting, but both Van Capelleveen et al. (2023) and Markou et al. (2025) seemingly underestimate the connection between all the aspects of materials passports, and work or skills. Van Capelleveen et al. (2023) discuss Honic et al. (2021) to show the effort that goes into producing a material passport using archival materials, visual inspection and laser scanning. A version of this process, focused on reuse, is documented in ReCreate's pre-deconstruction audit guideline (Vullings et al., 2022). Beyond the use of BIM and laser scanners (documented in Section 3.4.1), a skill/task that would be required is the archival work. Architects and designers working with refurbishment of existing buildings are used to working with archival material. A regular pre-demolition audit also requires some archival work, but a material passport for reused products would involve more details. Van de Capelleveen et al. (2023) and Markou et al. (2025) are focused on the stakeholders. One can infer that one or more stakeholders need extensive data management skills for managing materials in a production value chain environment. Currently, laser scanners, as used by the ReCreate partner Lagemaat mentioned below, is one example of combining human vision and electronic data gathering. In the context of the ReCreate project, information about materials and projects have been stored in a kind of 'data warehouse'. The project has been working on a Digital Element Database, which introduces an intended workflow to develop a database of precast concrete elements reclaimed from deconstructed buildings. The database includes flexible data on dimensions, material properties, and (historical) national standards.

In terms of skills, it appears that the circular construction economy could give birth to a new class of experts: those that know of materials/products, data management, and regulations, perhaps expanding the duties of architects and engineers. In the context of the ReCreate project, data management, material/product knowledge and knowledge of regulations has been a collective effort by the partners involved, which as such also bears the hallmark of their respective organisations. In the future, there may be specialised coordinators who oversee the data management of the project throughout the whole value-chain rather than the data management in a single company.

3. Skill needs of professions

It is impossible to fully predict what the future skill needs in the circular construction sector will be, but based on the empirical material from ReCreate's pilots, there are some clues. In what follows, the data will be analysed in the broad terms set in the previous chapter.

3.1. Deconstruction

Although reusing reclaimed elements in new buildings is an equally big part of the ReCreate output, deconstruction has proven to be the most spectacular in terms of new work processes. This is true although the ReCreate partners Ecosoil GmbH and Lagemaat BV have considerable experience in deconstruction, and there have been earlier examples of deconstruction too (see Huuhka et al., 2023).

Deconstruction sits in many ways at the heart of the circular construction economy. The goal of reuse is motivated by the need to reduce emissions, and buildings represent vast amounts of embodied carbon. Deconstruction, as opposed to demolition, is aimed at preserving past embodied carbon investments and capitalising on them in new construction projects. As environmental impact assessment shows, deconstruction also has its 'emission cost', but the savings in emissions compared to traditional demolition and new constructions are enormous (Huuhka et al., 2023).

Deconstruction professionals therefore have great responsibility for dismantling a building in such a way that products can be (relatively easily) reused. As experiences from ReCreate's deconstruction pilots show (Vullings et al., 2022; 2024a; 2024b), deconstruction is in a fundamental way a group effort. A deconstruction company may execute the physical deconstruction process, but before, during and after this process, other actors are deeply involved. Obviously, the amount of cooperation with other actors depends on the business model (see also Sairanen, 2023).

Interviews with deconstruction professionals show that new deconstruction skills are developed in a work context, i.e. these skills are not taught in vocational schools. Deconstruction in the way it is done by the ReCreate actors is such a specialised skill that it is unlikely (according to the respondents) that it will be taught in vocational schools unless it becomes common practice. However, there are transversal skills that can be taught already in vocational schools.

The first transversal skill need to be emphasised in the circular construction sector is *communication*. It goes without saying that, given the dangers of deconstruction work, communication skills and processes must be top-notch within the company and within the team working at the deconstruction site. Beyond this, communication includes planning work, in-situ decision making, and information processing. These tasks are executed by the people in charge of such decisions, but the aspect of communication, especially to external actors, like environmental authorities or subcontractors, is highly important. This is because

information sharing faces structural barriers due to the low level of vertical integration in the construction sector supply chain (see Wijewickrama et al., 2021). The planning work a deconstruction company has to engage in relates to permits, financing, and site management, but first and foremost to the deconstruction planning. In all ReCreate pilots, but especially in Finland and the Netherlands, the deconstruction company has been in close contact with structural engineers to plan the deconstruction. Although the former (literally) knows the nuts and bolts of deconstructing a building, they need the contribution of structural engineers to co-plan a process that does not compromise the structural integrity of the building. This may be necessary for permits. Communication skills are also needed for site planning. Construction projects are never simple, but the material flows of a deconstruction site are more complicated, as the building, deconstructed products, and recycled materials have to be pre-processed to some extent before leaving the site. For example, the Finnish deconstruction pilot involved planning how to lift the concrete elements. At the practical level, this included deciding lifting methods, crane positioning, logistics tendering, fine-tuning processes with the element factory (to minimise costs in refurbishing), etc. In planning the lifting methods, many issues were considered by the actors involved. The meetings combined a focus on communication with strong knowledge of the trade. Some methods were rejected on the basis of work safety, e.g. because of the tools involved and the potential risks these harboured. Other potential hoisting solutions were rejected because they were too complicated in practice, or equipment could not be made available in time. Also the project environment was important for planning: an annual ReCreate meeting in the Netherlands affected views on appropriate lifting methods. In the Dutch case, the content of deconstruction planning was similar to the Finnish case but because the Dutch partner had more prior experience with deconstruction, there was less novelty to the methods (from the point of view of the partners). The Swedish cluster's deconstruction took place prior the project start, perhaps due to which there were issues with storing and handling of the elements.

The second technical skill need for deconstruction companies is material and product knowledge. This issue had been discussed above, but at the practical level, this means the selection of the right tools for the job, and the employee with the skills to use them. A good example can be witnessed from the start of the Finnish deconstruction pilot. The façade elements were fastened differently than indicated on the archival drawings, so the deconstruction team, together with the structural engineers, had to find a safe solution. Material knowledge and recognition of the actual construction manner ultimately led to the 'improvisation' of a method that was fast and safe. Another example from Finland on material knowledge that intersects with communication relates to estimating the weight of the concrete elements. This was essential for lifting, as a tower crane needs the information on weight in order to set the lifting power correctly (which connects to work safety). Weight information was less relevant in the Netherlands and Germany because of the type of crane involved (hydraulic) and the availability of information. In the Finnish case, the structural engineers estimated the weight of element types, but in practice it was work of the crane driver to keep track of the actual weight of the different element types. Material knowledge has been involved also in using a demolition robot to remove screed and in using motorised diamond saws. These tools are needed to do the heavy work, and the deconstruction

workers manage the settings of the tools. This is necessary to get precise cuts on the elements and requires both knowledge of how the material reacts to the tools and precise instructions from the site manager. Setting the tools, e.g. cutting depth, is an essential skill to avoid inadvertent damage and value loss to adjacent elements (see also Vullings et al. 2024a).

Additionally, a combination of material knowledge and communication must be strengthened in circular construction, as deconstruction companies and refurbishing factories are connected in these processes. In order to prevent excessive and slow in-situ inspections, the partners in the project (lead by the structural engineers) have to design an in-situ assessment process that is simple and does not result in wrongly rejected products. This places high demands on the deconstruction workers, as their decisions can affect the total value and cost of the products reclaimed. Section 3.6 will discuss multi-actor processes in the context of education.

The third important future skill need for deconstructors is in digitalisation. Digitalisation of processes can be seen as the glue between the phases in circular construction. In ReCreate's deconstruction pilots, digitalisation had a primary role in deconstruction planning by way of the BIM-based deconstruction audit (see Vullings et al., 2022). Digitalisation in this sense involves also a lot of conversion of analogue materials, e.g. construction drawings and other archival materials, to digitised data. The importance of BIM-based methods will increase over the years, as the EU promotes the use of these methods and aims to integrate them with e.g. LCA frameworks like LEVEL(S)²⁶. The experience of the Finnish and Dutch clusters is slightly different compared to the German process: in Finland, the initial inventory model of the deconstruction pilot was made by the architecture studio partner LIIKE OY and adjusted by the structural engineers of Ramboll. In the Netherlands, point-cloud scanning and research on archival documents was mainly done by the deconstruction partner Lagemaat BV. In the German cluster, P. Jähne Ingenieurbüro GmbH uses software which is BIM-ready but employ it for 'regular' 3D models. The German partners did produce a BIM-model, nonetheless. In all cases, during the actual deconstruction, digitalisation played a minor role. The BIM models provided information to plan the deconstruction in the Dutch and Finnish cases, but in practice deconstruction is too dirty and dangerous to have workers continuously use digital tools. The site office in Finland was based around a paper map of the building and a whiteboard with daily and weekly goals and processes. The logistics of the reclaimed elements was partly digital, as the elements were labelled and entered into the refurbishing factory's system. From the point of deconstruction work, however, digitalisation had a minor role on site. In the context of knowledge management, the digital skills needed by construction workers in reuse arguably is higher than in the current linear, optimised construction sector. For example, in the deconstruction phase, the process of dismantling may cause unintentional variations in elements, which should already be documented. Element-specific photographs can easily be added to digital models of the donor building. In this way, information of the current state of objects can be used already for planning of subsequent phases. In the

²⁶ https://environment.ec.europa.eu/topics/circular-economy/levels_en

Finnish case, the site managers followed deconstruction in real time digitally too, with Excel-based accounting. During the deconstruction itself the dirty and dangerous work favoured the use of walkie-talkies, but at times smartphones was possible too.

3.1.1. The use of tools as an educational need

In deconstruction, the use of tools and machines is a core skill. In the ReCreate pilots, there have not been fully new tools in use. The tools used in the deconstruction pilots, ranging from robots to blowtorches, can be found in Vullings et al. (2024a: Section 4.2). However, the context of the tool use may be different from what workers were used to, and the tool use has implications for quality and further reuse opportunities. For example, diamond saws (Figure 1) are necessary to cut the connections between floor elements (see also Vullings et al. 2024a: 44-49). The use of these saws is not new, for example they are used in building adaptation processes. Regarding quality control, it is important that the sawing is done exactly according to the drawings, so that there will be no accidental damages to the elements, pillars or beams (cf. Vullings et al. 2024a). This is a practical skill that can be learned easily. Another implication from circular saw use is unavoidable – because the sawing blade is circular, sawing to the end of a seam means there will be (repairable) damage to adjacent elements (e.g. beams, columns, walls).

Figure 1. A diamond saw in use. Photo: Tampere University / Eetu Lehmusvaara.

The use of a demolition robot is also not new, but as mentioned above in the context of material knowledge, its use to remove screed has been new. Learning to operate machinery like this is company-specific and is not necessarily available in educational institutions. In the case of the robot, the manufacturer has national 'academies' to provide education for the use of its machines. This is a common model in the construction sector. From paint producers to vendors of safety harnesses, there are usually available product-specific

after-sales educational services. However, these concern only basic functionalities rather than what to use these machines for.

Another example of a tool for which after-sales training can exist is the lifting equipment (Figure 2). A typical way of lifting is to drill holes in the concrete elements, through which chains are looped and secured to the crane safely. In Finland and the Netherlands, slightly different methods (and cranes) were used to lift the concrete elements, but in both cases it involved a component of work safety (see Vullings et al., 2024a: Section 3.5). The Finnish pilot used a custom-designed and produced locking device to ensure safe lifting. In Finland, the attaching of loads to a crane must be done by an employee who has done a short certification course on this issue. During the course, practical aspects take centre stage, but equally important is learning how to communicate with the crane driver. In other ReCreate project countries these kinds of trainings exist, but during the Finnish deconstruction pilot, one was offered to all employees on site (including the researchers) for safety reasons. In Germany, the lifting could be performed differently, because the original lifting anchors were still present and could be used after safety checks (see Vullings et al. 2024a: 32-34). Also, because of the different type of construction, no columns or beams were reclaimed because the construction type does not employ these.

Figure 2. Lifting a concrete slab in the Dutch pilot project. Photo: Lagemaat BV.

All in all, the educational needs in deconstruction focus on material and product knowledge and knowing the tools of the trade. Some methods (e.g. using diamond saws) may be taught in vocational schools, but others, like the use of demolition robots, are taught at company- or product-specific courses. Furthermore, demolition/deconstruction is one of the few 'last resorts' for people with little education, so in the case of potential scaling up of deconstruction, these companies could provide new employment opportunities. Regardless of the scale of the circular project, the deconstruction company is the actor that does the heavy lifting (pun not intended). However, to be able to do this, the deconstruction

company is dependent on a multitude of information and data on materials and processes, which must in part be provided by other actors. The actors involved in the ReCreate project indicate that most of these 'new' skills are acquired while working rather than in school. What is more, even though traditional demolition is a kind of 'last resort' for people with the least education, deconstruction involves skills that are more evolved. Based on data from the Finnish deconstruction pilot, it is likely that these skills can also be acquired by on-the-job training, but in the future it may be necessary to teach some of these skills at the lowest educational levels, so this sector can still provide employment prospects for people that otherwise have difficulty to connect with the labour market. The deconstruction work provides opportunities for upskilling, which could already be integrated in general construction sector schooling. Increased skill demands regarding communication and digitalisation could provide an impetus for greater attractiveness of the sector for all genders.

But more than the skills above, reuse demands a new mindset – something that in German is called *umdenken* ('rethink' comes close). This is a fundamental change in approach for all professions involved: working with something existing, rather than starting from zero, is an idea – a starting point – that should be taught. Reuse implies a different understanding towards the built environment: rather managing resources than 'making' something from scratch.

3. 2. Precast concrete factories

In the ReCreate project, precast concrete manufacturing plants of the Consolis Group have been involved in the pilots: Consolis Parma in Finland, Consolis VBI in the Netherlands and Consolis Strängbetong in Sweden. The discussion of educational needs of this sector is short because on the one hand, the quality control tests performed derive from existing testing standards on virgin materials and concrete structures. However, the main difference is that with virgin production, testing methods and standards are used for controlling the consistency of the factory operations and outputs, while in reuse, these tests and standards can be used for the purpose of assessing durability or material properties of already existing elements. Furthermore, there are also standards and tests for structural survey of existing concrete constructions that can also be drawn from for this purpose.

On the other hand, refurbishing concrete elements after deconstruction also does not significantly diverge from activities that are performed occasionally with new products. Interviews revealed that sometimes, new prefabricated elements must be adapted or repaired in ways that resemble the refurbishment of reclaimed elements. However, the refurbishing process in the ReCreate project has so far only been performed in the Finnish case (at the time of writing). In circular construction projects, refurbishing in some form is always needed. One development need arose from the Finnish cluster. As the concrete element factory used normally produces façade elements, the workers do not necessarily have all the experience needed to work with structural aspects of other types of elements. For refurbishment, this means that the elements must be transported to specialised factories, factories must develop a broader range of skills of their employees, or they have

to invest in employee rotation schemes. In the Finnish pilot, the employee refurbishing the reclaimed elements does in fact come from a different production location.

The concrete manufacturing companies have played a vital role in quality control (see Räsänen et al. 2024a; 2024b). However, the tests do not necessarily have to take place at the manufacturer's facilities. In Sweden, the tests were performed by Research Institutes of Sweden RISE. In the Finnish case, certain tests were performed in the pre-deconstruction phases by Ramboll, and some full-scale tests (beams, columns, and/or connections) were or will be done at the Tampere University (TAU) construction laboratory. Structural testing has been performed similarly in Finland, Sweden and the Netherlands (see e.g. ReCreate 2024). Even though the universities, too, have equipment for testing hollow-core slabs, their structural tests were performed at a hollow-core slab factory (Figure 3). Such factories have appropriate equipment and experience, as this kind of testing is also part of quality assurance for new products. What is more, the manufacturers already have extensive test facilities for e.g. the development of low-cement or polymer concretes. If the ReCreate process of deconstruction can be scaled up, it may be efficient for concrete manufacturers to invest in skills and knowledge to perform some of the quality control tests. However, it may be sufficient that these skills can be found from consulting firms like Ramboll, although the best expertise for specific demanding products, like hollow-core slabs, lies with the producer. Regarding structural tests, the manufacturers have the necessary tools and skills, although external laboratories may also be used (universities or commercial laboratories).

Figure 3. Full-scale load testing of reclaimed hollow-core slabs at Consolis Parma facilities. Photo: Tampere University / Satu Huuhka.

Refurbishing reclaimed elements (Figure 4) is another core commitment of the manufacturers in the ReCreate project. The organisation of the Finnish cluster and the tasks that Consolis Parma agreed to enable the Finnish cluster to be the first in ReCreate to engage in this activity. For the first Finnish mini-pilot on reuse, Consolis Parma refurbished a number of prefabricated hollow-core slabs, which primarily meant filling the lifting holes, repairing surface damage and sawing the slabs to the correct measurements. According to factory personnel, these kinds of restorations are occasionally done with new elements as well. A difference is that in virgin materials, these operations are done when the concrete is still fairly soft, which means that is easier to handle. With harvested concrete, this advantage disappears. In addition, smaller alterations must be done with a handsaw. Refurbishing involves potentially complicated lifting logistics, with implications for work safety. The factory where the elements are refurbished is formally a factory for façade elements. Therefore, in the piloting phase, refurbishing was custom work to a great extent. As Figure 4 shows, this involves sawing by hand, whereas the sawing of elements in a hollow-core slab factory could be done on the regular production line by an employee with experience of sawing hollow-core slabs. This issue has been mentioned in interviews several times, and the respondents see it as a major development for increasing efficiency in refurbishing.

Refurbishing elements, including testing, creates new data on the products. This data should be incorporated in a digital version. In a model where on the one hand, deconstruction companies and, on the other hand, precast concrete manufacturing plants, are key actors towards reuse of concrete elements, digitalisation of information is key. The idea of material passports is highly important, but its minimum content depends on the regulatory demands – although these may be different from the requirements that structural engineers have. In theory, laboratory tests could provide a nearly endless amount of information, but at a monetary cost, and the material passport could also include information on the original location of specific elements. In the design of ReCreate's Dutch reuse pilot, the Circular Center Netherlands by Lagemaat, this information is taken into account in redesign. A key take-away is that the management of material passports is one new educational skill that could emerge as a need. It is unclear who should be the lead actor, but it is evident that the information provided for the material passport must be produced by different actors. This information should be collected and processed by the lead. It is conceivable that the information content of the material passport grows from its transition from one actor to another, which then means there has to be some kind of standard on its processing. It also implies many actors must acquire the associated documentation skills, and the final owner of the material and its passport must be able to ascertain the veracity of the information. The veracity of the information can only be verified by having a clear and transparent methodology for data collection. This may have implications for liability for damages for the relevant contractual partners (e.g. the owner of the elements, the deconstruction company or the seller). Although outside the scope of this deliverable, civil law implications of reused materials, including warranty and liability, are a topic of attention regarding educational needs at the firm level (see Sitra, 2020).

Figure 4. Figure 4. Cutting a hollow-core slab for one of the Finnish mini-pilots at Consolis Parma. Photo: Tampere University / Emmi Salmio.

3. 3. Logistics

A large part of the circular economy depends on functional logistics. In ReCreate, reclaimed concrete elements have been transported to the precast concrete manufacturing plants or other sites (for storage, testing and refurbishing), universities (for testing) and to future construction sites. The logistics of transporting concrete elements from A to B (Figure 5) is not new and does not require new skills. However, logistics planning is rather more complicated, not only between donor building and reuse site but also during the process which translates reclaimed elements to reused elements. The deconstruction has to be carefully planned, as to what elements can be dismantled at a certain stage. They have to be transported to a temporary storage site if they cannot be reused immediately, and the elements might be transported to yet another site for refurbishment. All this requires sensible ordering of the elements (which starts on the deconstruction site), because these intermediate steps should involve as little reorganising of elements as possible. This issue has been reiterated in interviews with personnel of Consolis Parma. Internal logistics are important for smooth refurbishment processes, but equally important can contribute to improved work safety. It is important to minimise lifting and internal logistics if possible. This requires skills in logistics but also requires planning ahead in the deconstruction phase.

Compared to traditional demolition, there are different requirements to the transport company in freight briefs and transport vehicles, as the load consists of construction products rather than waste. Included in logistics could also be all the lifting procedures, i.e. using cranes. As already mentioned, this does not need new skills as such, but there may be a lack of information about the specific loads that should be lifted. Given the dangers involved, this requires vigilance from the tower crane operator, and an excellent command of the machinery, so the operator can assess how to safely lift and move the loads involved. These aspects are more a matter of experience than an educational need. One totally new element in logistics, which aids quality assurance as well, is labelling of elements and making the loads so that labelling can be easily seen when products are loaded and stored. The storage of elements itself is also a clear skill need. Hollow-core slabs have to be stored correctly lest they are not damaged. This means that whoever is responsible for storage must know enough about the product/material not to inadvertently damage them. In the Nordic countries, the climate conditions play yet another role in ensuring proper storage.

Figure 5. Transporting a concrete slab in the Dutch deconstruction pilot. Photo: Lagemaat.

In scaling up circular construction, logistics become more complicated, as materials and products may be reclaimed from different locations, at different moments. A main challenge for streamlining the circular construction economy remains matching supply and demand geographically and temporally. Solving this logistics issue depends on skill needs that likely requires many data sources and can potentially benefit from the use of artificial intelligence.

3. 4. Quality control

Quality management is an aspect of reuse of concrete elements which may see new (technical) skill needs. Measuring of product qualities is to some extent dependent on the

jurisdiction, because international testing standards often have a national implementation. Nonetheless, there is considerable harmonisation. Also the revised Construction Product Regulation (CPR)²⁷ addresses circular products, and the product requirements related to circular use of certain categories of products (see also Räsänen et al., 2024a; 2024b). Scaling up reuse implies greater demand for people who can perform the tests (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Non-destructive testing of the location and diameter of slab reinforcement (left, source: BTU), and uniformity testing with a non-destructive MIRA device (right, photo © Tampere University/Aapo Räsänen).

The reports show that regulatory demands are unclear at the moment, so even nationally, depending on the product at hand, a diverse set of test skills is needed. This includes skills in documentation for e.g. material passports. Therefore, education should include teaching about the current nationally and internationally required quality assurance tests, but these can be incorporated in curricula (for e.g. building surveyors) once the national test requirements have been clarified. Räsänen et al. (2024b) show the required quality assurance tests as they have currently manifested in the ReCreate pilots but later, ReCreate will also be putting forward a best practice proposal as to what these should entail in the future. Importantly, measuring product quality also involves specific skills in visual inspection, which currently may not be found in all concrete factories where elements can be refurbished, if their employees normally handle other types of elements. This skill is vital, as even small cracks may have impact on strength if they are in the wrong places.

The skills and knowledge of structural engineers should be sufficient to perform these kinds of tests, but in some jurisdictions (e.g., in the English-speaking world) the formal responsibility for quality assurance may belong to specially trained building surveyors,

²⁷ https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=OJ%3AL_202403110&qid=1734509467150

which also would have most knowledge and experience. It is assumed that because the tests are based on standards, building surveyors and/or structural engineers can perform them or learn to perform them.

Quality control also incorporates data management of the product information. In the ReCreate project, work on this issue is ongoing, but from the ethnographic fieldwork in the Finnish pilots, it is clear that quality control is highly dependent on co-operation and communication between actors. One key question being addressed is what information should be in the possession of which actor at what time. Future standardisation or optimisation of circular construction products will bear out the information needs, but it is expected that future skill needs of project managers and subcontractors revolve around understanding data needs of stakeholders in reuse projects.

3. 5. Structural engineers

The Finnish mini-pilot showed that, in that particular case, there are few new things in installing reclaimed hollow-core slabs. In a press release, ReCreate partner Skanska said that the installation of reclaimed hollow-core slabs did not differ from the use of new elements²⁸. This is a finding specific to the mini-pilot nonetheless, and the other reuse pilots in the ReCreate project will yield more data on the skills and processes needed for the use of reclaimed hollow-core slabs, beams and columns. However, although the installation phase was close to 'business as usual', there still are numerous novelties from a structural engineering point of view, such as how to deal with the (un)availability of product information, which is why they emphasise measuring and testing. In other cases, there may be a need to devise new types of connectors, or design new connections using existing skills. These are skills related to structural design, repair and condition investigation as well as degradation mechanisms, and these may not belong to the standard curriculum for all structural engineers. Although designing the reuse pilots is still going on, a mock-up in Germany was designed to test a new connector design, which tested the ease of practical construction work with reclaimed elements. Also in the Dutch and Finnish cases, structural engineers are much involved in solving new issues that come from reusing elements.

Interviews with civil engineers involved in the German, Dutch and Finnish pilots have shown that the interviewees do not feel like they need new (technical) skills as such – the core skill of engineers is using their basic knowledge and applying it to the present issue. Although a certain need of specialisation is needed, i.e. the structural aspects of different types of precast concrete elements, in general that knowledge is sufficient for structural engineers in circular construction. Seen from a bit further away though, through observations during the pilot planning in meetings, it appears there is an 'art' to engineering. It does appear that creative thinking and problem-solving skills are emphasised in the work of engineers in a reuse project. This may be a distinction between engineers with a specialisation in

²⁸ <https://www.skanska.fi/tietoa-skanskasta/media/uutiset/285259/Ensimmaisiet-uudelleenkaetyt-betonielementit-asennettu-Tampereella->

renovation, and engineers working on new construction. The former have a problem-solving mindset that can benefit reuse of materials and products.

As for transversal skills, structural engineers have an important role in *communication* with other actors, in addition to their substantive role. They have a direct role in the structural planning of deconstruction, and this may also include preparing in-situ assessment methods and designing structural parts of the deconstruction process, like the design of lifting devices. Furthermore, structural engineers must be skilled in documenting information, which may be necessary for permitting processes (e.g. the structural stability of a building during deconstruction) and the material passport. In the ReCreate project, there have been different processes regarding the role of structural engineering companies. The experience of deconstruction may influence the role of the structural engineering company, but deconstruction can only be planned safely with the involvement of structural engineers. With this in mind, it is difficult to make hard conclusions about which actor would be the primary actor in circular projects, as they can start from different needs and contexts. This nonetheless matters regarding the archival phase of the pre-deconstruction audit (Vullings et al., 2022), because the (selection of the) primary actor has an impact on data management issues.

An educational need which is urgent is more knowledge for structural engineers about the policy environment. In the German, Finnish and Dutch pilots, there have been complicated discussions with authorities about quality assurance procedures and the waste status of materials in the context of permitting (see Halonen et al. 2025). Here, it suffices to say that the policy environment around circular construction is in flux: policy priorities and strategic programs change rapidly at the national level (and more slowly at the EU level) and has apparent grey areas. More education or training around these policy themes could help especially structural engineers to construct the right kind of arguments towards the authorities. For example, in the Finnish pilot, the project partners (especially Ramboll and Tampere University) have been in intensive contact with local, regional and national authorities to gain clarity around the waste status of reclaimed concrete elements. It is therefore important that project leaders can ask authorities the right questions, i.e. 'speak the right language' to the authorities (see Jonker-Hoffrén, 2023). Another option is to use outsourced policy experts, but it may provide a competitive advantage to have internal policy experts.

3.5.1. Tools for structural engineering

For various testing processes, specialist equipment may be used. For example, the investigation of hazardous substances in the Finnish pilot project required the use of a device to perform tests on volatile organic compounds (VOCs). Proper use of such a device demands skills that are generally developed in working life rather than at the university.

In the ReCreate project, structural engineers have also used the common tools of their profession, such as computer-aided design (CAD) and BIM programmes. These are nowadays taught in universities and represent flexible tools for (de)construction plans, even though they have not been specifically used for that purpose. Software can also be improved for this purpose. A tool which has been developed in the context of the ReCreate

project is a plugin to 'Revit' BIM software (Figure 7), which can be used to make BIM models using reclaimed materials and perform structural calculations (ReCreate, 2023). The tool nonetheless presupposes the presence of data on reclaimed elements. There are tools to produce this data, many of which use light detection and ranging (LIDAR) based technology to make point clouds of objects. This point cloud can be used to create a 3D model of the

Figure 7. A screenshot of the ReCreate plugin. Source: Eindhoven University of Technology / Fred Mudge (see ReCreate, 2023).

donor building and its elements, which can be further developed into a BIM model with information from archival drawings and construction calculations.

Drawings and calculations are not tools, but artefacts that must be found and acquired by the deconstruction project (typically by architects). This takes up resources as its own process, as the documents are most often in paper format or scanned PDFs, or more rarely in old computer-aided design (CAD) formats. The deconstruction pilots in Finland, the Netherlands and Germany have included such an 'inventory phase'. The successful acquisition of original drawings and calculations depends mostly on whether they have been archived or not. There might be a difference in preservation time between architectural and structural drawings too. The original drawings are commonly deposited with the permit issuer, which means the retriever of the documentation should be able to navigate the diverging practices of local authorities. Structural drawings are nonetheless not necessarily updated, and manufacturers usually destroy their plans after 10 years. Furthermore, they may have been misplaced or not even deposited originally.

The latter issue points to a need for digital format for information and data. Currently, older construction drawings may only exist as drawings on paper. If digitised drawings are available, they are typically scanned pixel images of the paper versions. This means that the information these documents entail must be 'imported' from analog to a digital format

in order to use them to produce a BIM model. ReCreate develops 'blank' element objects for BIM, which have basic characteristics that can be edited to match a specific donor building. By doing so, the blank objects can be transformed into reclaimed element objects and finally into reused element objects. Thus, a certain generic data structure will be preserved but the files may gain additional information. This is a new element as regards reuse, although the use of BIM for information, including inventories and process information can be a normal part of the job also presently.

3. 6. Architects

The profession of architect is one of the professions for which EU regulation exists. The educational needs of architects are to some extent similar to those of structural engineers, but the focus is more on space than on products or materials. Directive 2005/36/EC²⁹ succinctly lists that architects should be able to understand and translate 'the needs of individuals, social groups and authorities as regards spatial planning, the design, organisation and realisation of structures, conservation and the exploitation of the architectural heritage, and protection of natural balances.' This Directive replaced Directive 384/85/EEC³⁰, which specifically regulated mutual recognition by EU Member States of diplomas, certificates and other evidence of formal qualifications in architecture, in order to enable freedom of establishment and the freedom to provide services³¹. The original Directive was replaced by the new Directive to consolidate in one document the regulated professions in the EU and to provide general rules pertaining to providing services as a foreign national in another Member State. Section 8 of the Directive concerns the profession of architects. Articles 1(a-k) list the requirements of a university education in architecture. This list explicitly mentions, in 1(h-i), that architects should have sufficient understanding of structural design, constructional and engineering problems associated with building design and adequate knowledge of physical problems and technologies of buildings. However, European Court of Justice Case C-477/13 *Bayerischen Architektenkammer v Hans Angerer* determines that the required skills of architects should always be defined in the light of the legislation of the host Member State³².

A recent amendment lists the educational requirements for architects by country³³. Directive (EU) 2018/2001³⁴ on the promotion of renewable energy states that 'there is a further need to ensure that architects and planners properly consider an optimal combination of renewable energy sources and high efficiency technologies in their plans and designs.' Furthermore, it (preamble 21) asks Member States to 'take due account of the

²⁹ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/en/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32005L0036>

³⁰ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dir/1985/384/oj/eng>

³¹ <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/factsheets/en/sheet/40/freedom-of-establishment-and-freedom-to-provide-services>

³² <https://curia.europa.eu/juris/document/document.jsf?text=&docid=164553&pageIndex=0&doclang=EN&mode=lst&dir=&occ=first&part=1&cid=9729258>

³³ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32024D1395&qid=1740552610698>

³⁴ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32018L2001&qid=1740552549564>

principles of the circular economy and of the waste hierarchy.’ From these high-level documents, whose nominal purpose is to strengthen the EU internal market, it can be inferred that through this regulation, architectural education should also incorporate circular economy aspects. This conclusion seems to be strengthened by Directive (EU) 2018/844³⁵ on the energy performance of buildings (preamble 10), which states that Member States ‘should take into account the need for a clear link between their long-term renovation strategies and pertinent initiatives to promote skills development and education in the construction and energy efficiency sectors.’ This seems to broadly apply to architects and structural engineers.

According to interviews with the architects involved in ReCreate, the challenge for the profession of architects is greatest regarding the approach to design: architects will design new buildings (Figure 8), and architects are (as shown in the Directives above) involved in all phases of the construction. This role likely grows in reuse. Architects can create BIM objects of products to be reused (such as in the ReCreate plugin). A good example is the use of façade elements in the sports club building in Kolkwitz, for which the German ReCreate partners are also designing an extension. The reused façade elements provide the building with its own character. This solution points to the value of creatively considering possibilities of reclaimed elements.

Figure 8. Architect's impression of the German reuse pilot in Hohenmölsen. Source: BTU Senftenberg.

On the basis of empirical material available on the topic of design for reuse (ethnographic fieldnotes), it appears that in the case of reuse, architects have to be more aware of the product characteristics of reclaimed construction products, as it may not always be

³⁵ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex%3A32018L0844>

possible to realise any kind of space from them due to structural engineering constraints. It can be said that architects are concerned with space enclosed by the structures. At this moment, the observation about the Dutch pilot is just one data point, but it refers to a need to strengthen the understanding of structural engineering aspects in architectural design. The main challenge for architects lies in the deviation from the standard design process. With current technology, concrete elements can be custom designed and produced, which enables a clear division of labour between architects and structural engineers. Architects produce the design, which the structural engineer then aims to implement. The use of reclaimed elements necessarily changes this process, as the elements available in donor buildings constrain structure as well as space. This indicates a need for closer cooperation between architects and structural engineers when using reclaimed elements. For this reason, research on typologies of prefabricated elements is vital to be able to scale up reuse, especially to the benefit of cooperation between architects and structural engineers.

3. 7. Multi-actor processes

In the deconstruction and reuse processes of the ReCreate project, there have been few stages that have truly been handled by a single entity only. This is generally true of construction projects, which usually have multiple subcontractors and lots of different stakeholders. However, where circular construction perhaps differs from linear construction is that there is not yet a mature model of how such projects should be organised and led. In the Netherlands and Germany, the deconstruction pilots were led by deconstruction firms and the reuse pilots will also be guided by the same companies. However, this does not have to be the case. In the Finnish pilot, the construction company (Skanska) has been a major driver of the process, with other companies responsible for sub-phases of the deconstruction and reuse processes.

At the moment, there do not seem to be inherently better or worse models for leading these kinds of projects, but the involvement of many actors does require a lot from the leading actor, especially regarding formal processes like building permit applications. There are different ways to organise the processes, and various actors may be responsible for different regulatory aspects. The main requirement is that the necessary information is gathered, documented and transferred to other relevant actors. Supervising this kind of information flow would benefit from specialised managers, who are usually engineers or architects with expertise or training in construction project management. As indicated above, circular construction demands expertise on data management and communication. Some of these needs can be included in the university curriculum, but these skills relate to experience with the material world too: data management includes knowing what to know when, what steps to take for sustainable data preservation, data related to certain details of a project etc. Experience with operating data management technology/tools is needed too, but it is expected that skills with these tools are more often acquired in working life. One thing is certain: circular construction adds (even more) complexity to project management.

4. Discussion and conclusions

So far, the ReCreate project implies that with current skills and under current legislation, deconstruction and reuse of prefabricated concrete elements is possible. This is a very positive result from the view of the Green Transition: it would seem that a lot of 'brown' (i.e. polluting) occupations can be 'greened', as the demanded skills are already present. But on a practical level, the construction sector must be greened in other ways primarily, because also in the future, new materials will be needed. However, the Green Transition also faces many challenges other than those related to work and skills, as currently only the Swedish reuse pilot has been completed. More research is needed, but in the Dutch reuse pilot it seems that design iterations lead to a need to reassess structural matters. It appears relatively small changes may have large impacts, in terms of workload, for other professions. This is a small example of the need to more cooperation between architects and structural engineers, and the need for more knowledge about structural engineering for architects. Another matter, which is connected to skills and business models, is to what extent pilot partners effectively can communicate their plans to the local authorities to gain building permits (Jonker-Hoffrén, 2023).

In the totality of the project and its pilots, it seems the most crucial emerging 'green' skills are those that have to do with understanding policy, data management and communication. The first two skills are linked together through e.g. the idea of material passports. Although the ReCreate project has not created material passports in the regular sense, a lot of data has been gathered, managed and communicated. Like already proposed in a previous ReCreate report (Jonker-Hoffrén, 2023), there is a need of information/data at different stages in the value chain; data which is produced by different actors and which actors *need* in different phases to do work that benefits other actors later on. There are many studies on data management in construction, but in circular construction, firms have to determine or negotiate with other firms who should be the main holder of the 'data lake'. This function could also be taken up by a new actor, a new kind of business. This is not a skill need as such but seems closer to politics and contractual negotiations. This is also related to the ownership issues mentioned in Halonen et al. (2025) and Sitra (2020).

Interviews with the project partners suggest that to a large extent, educational needs could be filled at the place of employment. This follows the logic that during education, people learn general skills, and at the workplace, they acquire skills that are needed at that firm and for specific projects. That being said, it appears that throughout the value chain that it would be important to strengthen knowledge about materials and products, and how their characteristics change through their life.

One matter that connects policy and construction processes are LCA calculations. Currently, there are already many digital solutions and consultancy services to provide estimates of the whole life carbon emissions of a building. These calculations are often based on national product databases, with data provided by producers (like in the

Netherlands) or generic data (like in Finland) or a combination of generic and Environmental Product Declaration (EPD) based data (like in Germany). LCA data of reused products is not yet available generally, and data collection may be more complex than with virgin products. The reason is the LCA rules, because these determine what phases of the donor building's life cycle should be incorporated to the reclaimed product's life cycle in reuse. Firms (that 'produce' or sell reclaimed elements), will have to be able to acquire services, or learn in-house, to gather LCA data for reclaimed materials, and these data can be used to acquire Environmental Product Declarations (EPDs) for products. This requires a variety of skills and services from producers and re-users, in the realm of data management and quality assurance, which may enlarge the need for this kind of skills. This is a sphere of the labour market which is primarily policy-driven: permitting requirements set the needs for such calculations. The LCA data collection process involves much more than the construction products; very detailed information is needed about tools, processes, employees, locations etc. With these items, we come back to the importance of data management and data collection. Some data items require knowledge about work processes (planned or executed, up- and downstream the circular value chain) and the policy environment (requirements for environmental permits, for example).

Data and knowledge about the LCA data collection also feeds into another job that is emerging, although not present in the context of the ReCreate project: Environmental, social and corporate governance (ESG) reporting. Due to European regulations, such as the EU Taxonomy³⁶ and the Directive on Corporate Sustainability Reporting (CSRD)³⁷, large firms (and in the future SMEs) have a duty to report on the sustainability of their investments. This is in some way an accounting job, but given the complexity of the reporting, more knowledge of especially work processes of reuse is needed, because deconstruction as opposed to demolition has an impact on LCA scores (Al-Najjar et al., 2025).

In conclusion, in the context of the ReCreate project, which so far has included deconstruction, refurbishment, and some reuse (Swedish reuse pilot, mini-pilots and mock-ups in the Finnish and German pilots), the educational needs seem clear. On the one hand, there is a need for company-driven skill development. This can be either in using specialised tools or developing knowledge of specific test protocols. The tasks that have been observed in deconstruction, refurbishment, and reuse build on the employees' existing skills and knowledge, but the context is radically different. Rather than building with virgin materials, deconstruction results in reclaimed products, but skills are quite similar to new build skills, for most involved partners. Between deconstruction and demolition work, though, there is a large difference, as discussed in this report. Deconstruction, in the abstract, is inverted construction, which requires human labor. An emerging skill need, which likely mostly concerns architectural offices and structural engineering firms, is data management. This is a critical skill for the circular process itself, but also for current and

³⁶ https://finance.ec.europa.eu/sustainable-finance/tools-and-standards/eu-taxonomy-sustainable-activities_en

³⁷ https://finance.ec.europa.eu/regulation-and-supervision/financial-services-legislation/implementing-and-delegated-acts/corporate-sustainability-reporting-directive_en

future LCA calculations, which may soon have relevance for permitting. Furthermore, data management is critical for corporate sustainability reporting. On the receiving end of these processes, civil servants and financial institutions must have competences to rightfully process the data delivered. In the ReCreate project, there have been indications that local authorities do not always immediately have the technical knowledge, especially on quality assurance, needed for decision making (see Halonen et al., 2025).

4. 1. Limitations

This report does not directly touch upon skill needs for the public sector workforce. However, from the demands placed on quality assurance processes for permitting, it can be implied that the local authorities should know how to read such reports and be familiar with regulations pertaining to the circular economy.

This report also does not consider the employees whose task it is to gain financing for circular projects. This topic has come up in interviews and conversations, but in the context of the ReCreate project, this has not been pursued. In the context of the EU Taxonomy and other CSRD obligations, the link between the financial sector and the construction sector is likely important. Currently, it remains to be seen how the so-called Omnibus reform will affect sustainability reporting³⁸.

Finally, this report is based on information available in the ReCreate project and therefore reflects the context the project partners operate in. The ReCreate project enables industry partners to experiment and take risks, which means future deconstruction and reuse processes may proceed otherwise and result in different skill needs.

³⁸ https://finance.ec.europa.eu/publications/commission-simplifies-rules-sustainability-and-eu-investments-delivering-over-eu6-billion_en

5. Recommendations

The skill needs described in this report do not easily lend themselves to specific recommendations for educational institutions. A few general ideas can nevertheless be presented.

University education of engineers and architects

The ReCreate project, through deconstruction pilots and the ongoing reuse pilots, has shown that many phases of circular construction rely on adaptation of existing skills and knowledge. In particular, education relating to renovation of existing buildings seems to offer much of the knowledge needed for circular construction. Learning of test protocols, regulation and the assessment of structural stability for deconstruction are educational goals that build on existing curricula. What is perhaps most important, is facilitating and emphasising cooperation between architects and structural engineers. In reuse of concrete elements, the structural characteristics and dimensions are usually given, so these professional groups must work together to make reuse work both spatially and structurally. This implies that architectural education may benefit from more engagement with structural engineering studies and vice versa.

Extending material and product knowledge

Students in vocational schools do not have to learn to calculate force distributions in precast concrete, but in the context of deconstruction processes, it may be useful to learn about the behaviour of such materials and products. The reason is that a shared knowledge base about materials and products eases communication in work processes. University students need to know how hands-on work is conducted, in order to be able to reserve and estimate the spaces need for work processes. This may help build a shared understanding of what is not only theoretically but also practically possible. For example, knowledge of tools needed for deconstruction would benefit students of structural deconstruction design.

Cross-institutional projects

To grow a shared understanding of (de)construction processes in which products are reused, it would be extremely important to engage in shared pilot projects, in which students from different educational levels and fields (de)construct and reuse together, involving all stages of the project from planning to execution. This way, students will learn how to share data, and skills and at what stage data of one process is produced for a future stage.

Integration with public policy studies

The policy environment around the circular economy is continuously changing in the EU. Therefore, it is useful there are many organisations that offer webinars or workshops on policy developments. It is not always clear what their audience is, but it can be assumed that the most important information is disseminated to others in participants'

organisations, regardless of the participants being architects, structural engineers or ESG managers. However, also at the university education level there could be more attention to policy issues for architects and structural engineers. The primary reason is that the logic of policymaking and decision-making is based on what the law says to be scope of rules, and civil servants can make decisions only on this basis. Observations in the Recreate project have shown that this fact sometimes creates friction, because circular solutions do not always neatly fit into existing categories. Furthermore, it is likely useful to integrate other fields, such as accounting and architecture or structural engineering here too. EU corporate sustainability reporting rules may have future impact on the intra-organisational reporting requirements for these profession (e.g. primarily regarding documenting decisions concerning material use or predicted LCA values) Therefore, this is an aspect of business administration. Circular economy implies that the many parts of the supply chain are part of a greater whole. This should be acknowledged in education.

Integration with data science studies and ICT

Given the growing need for data management in circular economy -based construction, it is likely useful to integrate various disciplines with courses in data management processes and ICT. For this to successfully happen, software developers nonetheless first have to learn about deconstruction and the data needs that appear in those processes. The data environment of circular construction is complicated (and certainly not yet mature), which opens up an avenue for innovation and multi-disciplinary learning. Proprietary software may also be a barrier to innovation and cooperation, but it can be assumed that universities use the same software in teaching as the majority of the sector.

6. References

- Al-Najjar, A., Malmqvist, T., Stenberg, E., & Höjer, M. (2025). Stock, flow and reuse potential of precast concrete in Swedish residential buildings: Embodied carbon assessment. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, 218, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2025.108229>
- Ayodele, O.A., Chang-Richards, A. & González, V. (2020). Factors affecting workforce turnover in the construction sector: A systematic review. *Journal of Construction Engineering and Management*, 146(2), [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)CO.1943-7862.0001725](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)CO.1943-7862.0001725)
- Brand, S. (1995). *How buildings learn: What happens after they're built*. Penguin.
- Burger, M., Stavropoulos, S., Ramkumar, S., Dufourmont, J. & van Oort, F. (2019). The heterogeneous skill-base of circular economy employment. *Research Policy*, 48(1), 248–261. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2018.08.015>
- Capelleveen, G. van, Vegter, D., Olthaar, M. & van Hillegersberg, J. (2023). The anatomy of a passport for the circular economy: a conceptual definition, vision and structured literature review. *Resources, Conservation & Recycling Advances*, 17, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rcradv.2023.200131>
- Collins, H. (2004). Interactional expertise as a third kind of knowledge. *Phenomenology and the cognitive sciences*, 3, 125–143.
- Collins, H. & Evans, R. (2007). *Rethinking Expertise*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press. <https://doi.org/10.7208/9780226113623>
- Debacker, W., Manshoven, S. and Denis, F. (2016). *Key barriers and opportunities for Materials Passports and Reversible Building Design in the current system*. Buildings as Material Banks Project. http://www.bamb2020.eu/wp-content/uploads/2016/03/D1_Synthesis-report-on-State-of-the-art_20161129_FINAL.pdf
- Deranty, J. P. (2009). What is work? Key insights from the psychodynamics of work. *Thesis Eleven*, 98(1), 69–87. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0725513609105484>
- Dervishaj, A., & Gudmundsson, K. (2024). From LCA to circular design: A comparative study of digital tools for the built environment. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, 200. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2023.107291>
- Einhorn, H. J., & Hogarth, R. M. (1987). Decision making: Going forward in reverse. *Harvard Business Review*. <https://hbr.org/1987/01/decision-making-going-forward-in-reverse>

Fielden, S. L., Davidson, M. J., Gale, A. W., & Davey, C. L. (2000). Women in construction: the untapped resource. *Construction Management & Economics*, 18(1), 113-121.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/014461900371004>

Frampton, K. (2001). *Studies in tectonic culture: the poetics of construction in nineteenth and twentieth century architecture*. MIT Press.

Halonen, T., Räsänen, A., Jonker-Hoffrén, P., Huuhka, S., Malmqvist, T., Al-Najjar, A., Vullings, M., Wijte, S., Fischer, J., & Henschel, C. (2024). *Legal and technical requirements in reusing precast concrete*. The ReCreate project. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13829045>

Halonen, T., Jonker-Hoffrén, P., Huuhka, S., Malmqvist, T., Appelqvist, T., Vullings, M.W.F., Houtman, J., Wijte, S.N.M., Mettke, A., Fischer, J. & Henschel, C. (2025). *Guide to national implementation differences of norms applicable to reuse*. The ReCreate project.

Honic, M., Kovacic, I., Aschenbrenner, P., Ragossnig, A. (2021) Material passports for the end-of-life stage of buildings: Challenges and potentials, *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 319, p. 128702, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2021.128702>

Huuhka, S., Aarikka-Stenroos, L., Lahdensivu, J., Jonker-Hoffrén, P., Arnold, V., Stenberg, E., Blok, R., Gudmundsson, K., Teuffel, P., & Mettke, A. (2023). Recreating the Construction Sector for Circularity: Catalysing the reuse of prefabricated concrete elements. *The Routledge Handbook of Catalysts for a Sustainable Circular Economy* (pp. 42-66). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003267492-4>

Jakonen, M., Jonker-Hoffrén, P., Kontturi, K.-K., & Tiainen, M. (2025). A Proposal for a Multidisciplinary Approach, in: Aavaranta, O. & Välimäki, S. (eds.) *Counterpoints of art and research: concepts, practices, and demarcations from the Finnish academia*. Art theoretical writings from the Academy of Fine Arts Vol 19. <https://urn.fi/URN:ISBN:978-952-353-475-9>

Jonker-Hoffrén, P. (2023). *Guide to Coalition Building for Circular Construction*. The ReCreate project. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13829029>

Kumar, P., Singh, A. B., Arora, T., Singh, S., & Singh, R. (2023). Critical review on emerging health effects associated with the indoor air quality and its sustainable management. *Science of The Total Environment*, 872, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2023.162163>.

Markou, I., Sinnott, D., & Thomas, K. (2025). Current methodologies of creating Material Passports: A Systematic Literature Review. *Case Studies in Construction Materials*, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cscm.2025.e04267>.

Maulden, R. (1986). *Tectonics in architecture: from the physical to the meta-physical* (Doctoral dissertation, Massachusetts Institute of Technology). <https://dspace.mit.edu/handle/1721.1/78804>

McGrath, J. (2021). *Report on labour shortages and surpluses*. Brussels: Publications Office of the European Union. https://www.ela.europa.eu/sites/default/files/2023-12/2021_Labour_shortages_surpluses_report.pdf

Mitera-Kielbasa, E., & Zima, K. (2024). BIM Policy Trends in Europe: Insights from a Multi-Stage Analysis. *Applied Sciences*, 14(11), 4363. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app14114363>

Pallasmaa, J. (2009). *The Thinking Hand: Embodied and Existential Wisdom in Architecture*. London: John Wiley and Sons.

ReCreate (2023). *BIM-software for designing with reused concrete building components*. <https://recreate-project.eu/2023/09/14/bim-software-for-designing-with-reused-concrete-building-components/>

ReCreate (2024). *Testing concrete elements a step towards circular construction*. <https://recreate-project.eu/2024/08/02/testing-concrete-elements-a-step-towards-circular-construction/>

Redlinger, L. J., & Shanahan, D. T. (1986). Planning forward and planning backward: Approaches to policy implementation. *Criminal Justice Policy Review*, 1(1), 76–90.

Räsänen, A., Lahdensivu, J., Vullings, M., Dervishaj, A., & Huuhka, S. (2024a). *Procedure for quality management of reclaimed concrete elements*. Reusing precast concrete for a circular economy. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13828914>

Räsänen, A., Lahdensivu, J., Gudmundsson, K., Dervishaj, A., Westerlind, H., Lambrechts, T., Vullings, M., Arnold, V., & Huuhka, S. (2024b). *Properties and quality of precast concrete elements deconstructed in ReCreate's pilots*. Reusing precast concrete for a circular economy. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13828948>

Sairanen, M. (2023). *Business Model Canvases for Precast Concrete Element Reuse*. The ReCreate project. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13829009>

SITRA (2020). *Rethinking ownership: producer ownership models in a Circular Economy*, <https://www.sitra.fi/app/uploads/2020/12/rethinking-ownership.pdf>

Supanti, D., & Butcher, K. (2019). Is corporate social responsibility (CSR) participation the pathway to foster meaningful work and helping behavior for millennials?. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 77, 8–18. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhm.2018.06.001>

Vullings, M., Wijte, S., & Huuhka, S. (2022). *Guidelines for a BIM-aided pre-deconstruction audit*. The ReCreate project. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13828691>

Vullings, M., Huuhka, S., Wijte, S., Lambrechts, T., Houtman, J., Salmio, E., Räsänen, A., Jonker-Hoffrén, P., Weijo, I., Lahdensivu, J., Wedelsbäck, C., Appelqvist, T., Gudmundsson, K., Dervishaj, A., Westerlind, H., Hernandez Vargas, J., Henschel, C., Fischer, J., & Gottschling, D.

(2024a). *Best practice guidelines and recommendations for reuse-optimised deconstruction*. The ReCreate project. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13828738>

Vullings, M., Wijte, S., Henschel, C., Fischer, J., Huuhka, S., Salmio, E., Räsänen, A., Lahdensivu, J., Gudmundsson, K., Stenberg, E., Westerlind, H., & Dervishaj, A. (2024b). *Real-life deconstruction pilots of the ReCreate project*. Reusing precast concrete for a circular economy. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13828855>

Wijewickrama, M. K. C. S., Rameezdeen, R., & Chileshe, N. (2021). Information brokerage for circular economy in the construction industry: A systematic literature review. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 313, 127938.

Wisner, A. (1995). Understanding problem building: Ergonomic work analysis. *Ergonomics*, 38(3), 595–605. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00140139508925133>